

आचारधर्मः - A Glance

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Dharmas can be basically classified into three as i) आचार धर्मः ii) व्यवहार धर्मः
iii) प्रायश्चित्त धर्मः | Of these three, let us have a clear glance of the आचार धर्मः |

आचार धर्मः --

Under this section आचार धर्मः, Samskaaras play a vital role, since they are the customary practices of our day to day life of our righteous Hindu Society.

Samskaaras -- The meaning, their role in Sutra literature and their number :

The word Samskaara is derived from the Sanskrit root “संस्कृष्यन्” and is used in a variety of ways. It corresponds with Sanskrit karman, religious act in general. It is seldom found in the early Vedic literature. But its allied word “samskrta” occurs frequently enough. In the Rgveda it is used in the sense of “purified” . “The two Aswins do not harm the gharma (vessel) that has been purified”. The Satapatha Brahmana uses the term in the sense of preparing or purifying Havis(offering) for the Gods. The Mimamsakas mean by it the Ceremonious purification of sacrificial materials. “प्रोक्षणादिजन्यसम्स्कारी यज्ञाङ्ग पुरोडाशेष्विति द्रव्यधर्मः” |⁶⁵

In the Sutras of sage Jaimini, the word Samskaara has been applied several times in the sense of some purificatory rite. Sabara, the commentator on the Jaimini sutras, explains the term Samskaara as an act which makes a certain thing or person fit for a certain purpose.

⁶⁵ वाचस्पत्यबृहदभिधानं 5.pg no 5188

“संस्कारो नाम स भवति यस्मिञ्जाते पदार्थो भवति योग्यः कस्यचिदर्थस्य”⁶⁶ “The Tantravaartika regards the term Samskaara as those acts and rites that impart fitness and further adds, “fitness is of two kinds”. It arises from the removal of taints (sins) Or by the generation of fresh qualities.

Samskaaras generate fresh qualities, while tapas brings about the removal of sins”. In the Classical Sanskrit literature, the word Samskaara used in a very wide sense :-- in the sense of education, cultivation, training, refinement, perfection and grammatic purity; making perfect, refining, polishing; embellishment decoration and ornament; impression, form, mould, operation, ambience; the faculty of recollection, impression on the memory; a purificatory rite, a sacred rite Or ceremony, consecration, sanctification and hallowing; idea, notion and conception; effect of work, merit of action etc.

So we find that the word Samskaara has got its own associations gathered around it through its long history. It means religious purificatory rites and ceremonies for satisfying the body, mind and intellect of an individual, so that he may become a fullfledged member of the community. The Samskaaras with their paraphernalia were regarded as producing a peculiar indefinable kind of merit for the man who underwent them as “a peculiar excellence due to the rites ordained in the body”.

“आत्मशरीरान्यतरनिष्ठः विहितक्रियाजन्योऽतिशयविशेषः सम्स्कारः”⁶⁷

It was in this collective sense that the word Samskaara was used. Though many of the Samskaaras originated in, or even before, the Vedic period, as the ritualistically specific hymns of the vedas indicate, the word “Samskaara” does not occur in the vedic literature. The Brahmana literature also does not mention the word, though some sections of it contain fragments of a few samskaaras like the उपनयनम्, श्मशानकर्म etc. The मीमांसकाः used the word in the sense of not purificatory rites concerning

⁶⁶ जैमिनिसूत्रम् 3.1.3

⁶⁷ वीरमित्रोदयं संस्कारप्रकाशः 1.132

individuals but in the sense of cleansing and purifying sacrificial materials before they were offered into fire. The work वाचस्पत्य - बृहदाभिधानम् says thus :

“त्रीह्यादेश्च यज्नाङ्गताप्रदानाय वैदिकमार्गेण प्रोक्षणादिः”⁶⁸

Apart from the above views, the entire Samskaras are grouped under the following five heads :

They are : 1) The Pre-natal Samskaras [from गर्भादानम् to सीमन्तोन्नयनम्

2) The Childhood Samskaras [from जातकर्म to चूडाकर्म]

3) The Educational Samskaras [from चूडाकर्म to समावर्तनम्]

4) The Marriage Samskaras [the विवाहकर्मणि]

5) The Funeral Ceremonies [the अन्त्येष्टिः]

Numbers of Samskaras :

The following are the number of Samskaras dealt within some of the ग्रहसूत्राणि | They fluctuate from twelve to eighteen and the lists are slightly varying in the names of some particular Samskaras.

The आश्वलायनग्रहसूत्रम् mentions a total of eleven Samskaras . They are as follows :

- 1) विवाहः (marriage) 2) गर्भालम्भनम् (conception) 3) पुग्मसवनम् (quickenning of male child) 4) अनवलोभनम् (protection from abortion) 5) सीमन्तोन्नयनम् (Hair-parting) 6) जातकर्म (Birth ceremony) 7) नामकरणम् (name-giving) 8) अन्नप्राशनम् (first feeding) are the four belong to childhood Samskaras; 9) चूडाकर्म(tonsure of hair) 10) उपनयनम् (Initiation through sacred thread ceremony) 11) समावर्तनम् (the end of studentship) are the three belong to Educational Samskaras and finally 12) अन्त्येष्टिः (last rites) belongs to Funeral Ceremonies.

Sage पारस्करः in his ग्रहसूत्रम् , also mentions the same as in the आश्वलायनग्रहसूत्रम् | But he includes the केशान्त सम्स्कारः as an extra ceremony under the Educational

⁶⁸ वाचस्पत्यबृहदाभिधानं 5.pg no 5158

Samskaras. Sage बौधायनः in his ग्रह्यसूत्रम् , also mention the same twelve types of Samskaras in addition to the two Samskaras namely उष्णिष्क्रमणम् (first outing of the child) and कर्णवेधनम् (Boring of the child's ears) belonging to the childhood Samskaras. But he mentions the word पित्रमेध सस्कारः instead of अन्त्येष्टि सस्कारः |

The गौतमधर्मसूत्रम् gives a list of altogether forty Samskaras with eight virtues of the Soul (चत्वारिंशत् गुणाः , अष्टौ आत्मगुणाः च) . They are as follows : 1) गर्भादानम् 2) पुग्मस्वनम् 3) सीमन्तोन्नयनम् 4) जातकर्म 5) नामकरणम् 6) अन्नप्राशनम् 7) चौलम् 8) उपनयनम् 9 to 12) चत्वारि वेदव्रतानि 13) स्नानम् 14) सहधर्मचारिणीसम्योगः 15 to 19) पञ्चमहायज्नाः 20) अष्टकाः 21) पार्वणः 22) श्राद्धः 23) श्रावणीः 24) आग्रहायणी 25) चैत्र आश्वयजी 26) सप्तपाकयज्जसमस्थाः 27) अग्न्यदेयम् 28) अग्निहोत्रम् 29) दर्शपौर्णमास्या 30) चातुर्मास्या 31) आग्रयानेष्टिः 32) निरूढपशुबन्धः 33) सौत्रामणि इति सप्तहविर्यज्जसमस्थाः 34) अग्निष्टोमः 35) अत्यग्निष्टोमः 36) उक्थः 37) षोडशी 38) वाजपेयम् 39) अतिरात्रम् 40) आसौर्यम् इति सप्त सोमयज्ज समस्थाः ||

The Smrtis generally by Samskaras only those sacramental rites that were performed for sanctifying the personality of an individual. According to मनुः , the स्मार्तसंस्काराः proper are thirteen from गर्भादानम् to अन्त्येष्टि सस्कारः | Beginning from गर्भादानम् to अन्त्येष्टि सस्कारः , they are as follows :-- 1) गर्भादानम् 2) पुग्मस्वनम् 3) सीमन्तोन्नयनम् 4) जातकर्म 5) नामकरणम् 6) निष्क्रमणम् 7) अन्नप्राशनम् 8) चूडाकर्म 9) उपनयनम् (Or) मौन्जीबन्धनम् 10) केशान्तः 11) समावर्तनम् 12) विवाहः and 13) श्मशानः |

मनुः himself says thus in his मनुस्मृति :---

निषेकादिश्मशानान्तो मन्त्रैर्यस्योदितो विधिः |

तस्य शास्त्रेऽधिकारोऽस्मिन्जनेयो नान्यस्य कस्यचित् ||⁶⁹

वैदिकैः कर्मभिः पुण्यैर्निषेकादिर्द्विजन्मनाम् |

कार्यः शरीरसंस्कारः पावनः प्रेत्य प्रेह च ||

गाभैर्जातकर्मचौडमौन्जीनिबन्धनैः |

⁶⁹ मनुस्मृतिः 3.70

बैजिकम् गार्भिकम् चैनो द्विजानामपरुज्यते ॥

प्राङ्नाभिवर्धनात्पुम्सो जातकर्म विधीयते ।

मन्त्रवत्प्राशनम् चास्य हिरण्यमधुसर्पिषाम् ॥⁷⁰

याज्ञवल्क्यस्मृतिः also enumerates the same Samskaras except the केशान्तः which was omitted from the list owing to decline of the Vedic studies and its confusion with the समावर्तनम् | The later Smritis supply the list of sixteen important Samskaras . According to the व्यासस्मृतिः the important Samskaras are : (i) गर्भादानम् (ii) निष्क्रमणम् (iii) अन्नप्राशनम् (iv) वपनक्रिया (v) कर्णवेधनम् (vi) व्रतादेशः (vii) वेदारम्भः (viii) केशान्तः (ix) स्नानम् (x) उद्वाहः (xi) विवाहाग्निपरिग्रहः and (xii) त्रेताग्निसङ्ग्रहः |

In this list, कर्णवेधनम् and the last two Samskaras are added to the number given in मनुस्मृतिः and याज्ञवल्क्यस्मृतिः | This late addition was due to the fact that कर्णवेधनम् was regarded as a Samskara only later, originally being meant for decoration.

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⁷⁰ मनुस्मृतिः 2.16,26,27,29